

**Thermoeconomic analysis of the Integrated Waste Energy Recovery System (IWERS) that
recovers residual heat from bakery oven steam**

Juan Carlos Ríos-Fernández

University of Oviedo, Department of Energy, Polytechnic School of Engineering of Gijón,
33203 Gijón (Asturias). Spain

Corresponding author

E-mail address: riosjuan@uniovi.es (Juan Carlos Ríos-Fernández)

Abstract

The evaluation of the Integrated Waste Energy Recovery System (IWERS) is based on thermoeconomic criteria over a year of operation. The system recovers heat from bakery ovens in supermarkets and other commercial facilities to heat domestic hot water, resulting in energy savings. The analysis examines the system as a whole and its components. The results indicate that the period of highest exergy destruction aligns with the hottest months of the year. During this period, the IWERS experiences a 4% decrease in exergetic performance, while the unit exergetic cost of the product increases by up to 4.2%. The study also reveals that the steam condenser is responsible for the highest relative exergy destruction, reaching nearly 45%.

Keywords: Integrated Waste Energy Recovery Systems (IWERS); Thermoeconomic; Exergetic evaluation; Exergetic efficiency; Heat recovery; Bakery oven

Abbreviations

DHW: domestic hot water

IWERS: Integrated Waste Energy Recovery Systems

°C: degrees Celsius

Nomenclature

Ex: exergy (kJ)

$\dot{E}x$: exergy flow rate (kW)

e: specific exergy (kJ kg^{-1})

h: specific enthalpy (kJ kg^{-1})

m: mass (kg)

\dot{m} : mass flow rate (kg s^{-1})

Q: heat transfer (kJ)

\dot{Q} : heat transfer flow rate (kW)

P: pressure (bar)

S: entropy (kJ K^{-1})

s: specific entropy ($\text{kJ K}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$)

T: temperature (K or $^{\circ}\text{C}$)

T_0 : average monthly/yearly temperature (K or $^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Greek letters

Σ : sum

Subscripts

ex: exergetic

i: i-th material stream

j: j-th instant

0: ambient or surrounding value

Superscripts

CH: chemical

KN: kinetic

PH: physical

PT: potential

+: incoming flows

-: outgoing flows

.: flow rate

*: exergetic cost

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoeconomics is a field that combines thermodynamic principles with economic analysis. It brings fundamental changes to the economic evaluation, design, and maintenance of energy systems [1]. It is typically defined as the application of thermodynamic principles and economic parameters to optimize the design and operation of thermal systems [2]. It applies the laws of statistical mechanics to economic theory, essentially treating economic value as a physical system [3]. Furthermore, the field of thermoeconomics involves the development and application of exergy and economy analysis, also known as exergoeconomics [2]. This field is a powerful tool for analyzing, diagnosing, and optimizing energy systems. It provides a deeper understanding of how human societies obtain and use energy [4]. Numerous scientific articles and research studies have contributed to the advancement of thermoeconomics, demonstrating its potential in optimizing and accounting for the costs of energy systems [5]. This way, thermoeconomics has become an essential area of research due to the increasing demand for natural and energetic resources and the signs of global warming. It aims to provide advanced tools to solve complex energy problems [6]. Thus, this discipline combines thermodynamics and economics, which provides a distinctive framework for analyzing energy systems. The exergetic cost theory is a key methodology in this field, introducing the concept of exergetic cost to the thermoeconomic domain [7]. This approach has significantly contributed to the comprehensive evaluation and optimization of energy systems, reflecting the intrinsic link between energy and economic considerations. The integration of thermodynamic principles with economic analysis has become increasingly essential in the study of this system and processes. It is particularly important in the context of rising global energy demands and the need for sustainable resource management.

The field of thermoeconomics has seen significant advancements in recent years. A special issue in the journal *Entropy* was dedicated to collecting original papers focused on thermoeconomic analysis, providing an overview of current research in the field and its potential applications [8]. Additionally, several research studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of thermoeconomic optimization and cost accounting in evaluating energy systems [5]. The integration of thermodynamic principles with economic analysis in the study of energy systems has become increasingly important. This is especially true in the context of rising global energy demands and the need for sustainable resource management [9]. Thus, thermoeconomic analysis is relevant for addressing complex energy problems.

The thermoeconomics literature classifies articles based on the facilities analyzed, covering a wide range of systems and facilities. It can be summarized as follows:

1. **Energy Systems:** Several articles focus on the thermoeconomic analysis and optimization of energy systems, demonstrating the application of thermoeconomics in this field [10-12].
2. **Cogeneration Systems:** Research has been conducted on advanced cogeneration systems, particularly in the context of buildings, with an emphasis on the application of thermoeconomic analysis in this specific area [13,14].
3. **Industrial and Thermal Systems:** Thermoeconomics has been applied to industrial and thermal systems, with a focus on cost accounting, optimization, and diagnosis of these facilities [4,15].
4. **Building Thermal Systems:** The use of thermoeconomics in building thermal systems is becoming increasingly important in promoting energy savings and reducing environmental impact [16,17].
5. **Various Systems and Plants:** The literature presents applications of thermoeconomic analysis in a wide variety of systems and plants, reflecting its diverse scope [18].

These classifications demonstrate the extensive applicability of thermoeconomics across different types of facilities. It ranges from energy systems to building thermal systems and is relevant in addressing complex energy challenges in various domains.

This article explores the applications and importance of thermoeconomics in the analysis and optimization of Integrated Waste Energy Recovery Systems (IWERS). The aim is to provide an

objective evaluation of this system for the utilization of the residual heat of the steam generated in the bread ovens of commercial establishments.

IWERS is a system used in grocery stores to take advantage of the residual heat generated in bread ovens. This system, described in detail in [19], uses the thermal energy of steam to heat domestic hot water (DHW).

2. METHODOLOGY

The systems subjected to thermodynamic analysis are usually sets of elements (equipment or components) connected to each other and to the environment by lines of matter and energy exchange. This characteristic is fulfilled by the IWERS. Figure 1 illustrates the components of IWERS that will undergo analysis, including their respective flows of matter, energy, and work.

Figure 1. Components of IWERS and flows of matter, energy, and work

Graph theory and linear algebra provide the necessary elements. Thus, an algebraic representation of the system structure is achieved through the incidence matrix, a vector representation of the matter and energy flows, and the execution of balances through matrix algebra. This way, the formal formulation of the problem is simplified, and the calculations can be repeated, as is usually required in systems analysis and synthesis tasks. To develop the thermo-economic analysis in a progressive way, a system must be considered at the maximum level of aggregation, i.e., in the form of a single unit or "black box". Figure 2 shows the IWERS under these conditions. All values of the thermo-economic route were obtained according to the theoretical developments of the research [20-24], as detailed below.

Incident Matrix

The incident matrix $A_{m \times n}$ represents the energetic connections of the system with its environment. Connections may involve flows of matter, heat, or exchange of work. The incidence matrix will have all its elements null, except those related to currents between the system and its environment, which will be +1 or -1, depending on whether they enter or leave the system. Where m is the equipment and n are the fluxes or currents.

Exergy Vector

The exergy vector corresponds to a matrix $B_{l \times n}$. The components of the matrix will be the exergy values per unit of time in each of the teams.

Exergy per unit of time or exergetic power of each piece of equipment

The mechanical work is pure exergy and therefore, if it exists, it will appear as \dot{W}_n . The heat flow would have to be multiplied by $(1-T_0)/T_i$. Where T_i is the temperature at which the heat transfer occurs. And \dot{B}_n represents the exergy flow that, if it exists, is not due to the transfer of heat or work done.

Diagnostic Vector

The diagnostic vector is calculated using the following equation:

$$B_{d(1xn)} = A_{(m \times n)} \cdot B_{(1xn)} \quad (1)$$

It represents the exergy that is destroyed in the equipment that makes up the system.

Total Exergy Destruction

\dot{B}_d represents the total exergy destroyed, or also the total thermodynamic savings theoretically possible. Since exergy is an extensive property, the destruction in the system is the sum of the exergy destroyed in each of the devices. This is:

$$\dot{B}_d = \sum_{i=1}^{i=m} \dot{B}_{d,i} \quad (2)$$

Each element $\dot{B}_{d,i}$ of the diagnostic vector B_d represents the exergy destroyed in generic equipment i , therefore, the maximum energy saving theoretically possible in it.

Exergy destruction rate

The comparison between $\dot{B}_{d,i}$ and the total exergy destruction gives an idea of the relative weight of each team in the exergy destruction or the total irreversibility of the system, through the exergy destruction rate d_i , defined as:

$$d_i = \frac{\dot{B}_{d,i}}{\dot{B}_d} \quad (3)$$

This rate is typically expressed as a percentage by multiplying it by 100.

The analysis of the installation can be done with as much detail as desired, down to each piece of equipment, or even breaking down some pieces of equipment into several elements. The level of aggregation decreases, and the incidence matrix becomes more complicated. If we do the reverse, grouping certain elements into subsets of the system, the level of aggregation is increased, and the incidence matrix is simplified. In each specific case, we used a sufficiently low level of aggregation to achieve the objectives of the analysis with the least possible complexity.

The first part of the methodology was based exclusively on thermodynamics without introducing economic considerations, such as what resources are consumed, what products are used, or what waste is generated in the system. The evaluation of the quality of the system and its components was based exclusively on their greater or lesser thermodynamic perfection. For the development of thermoeconomic analysis, it was necessary to resort to the application of economic value concepts and judgments. First, it was necessary to know the economic or productive structure of the IWERS. To do this, it is necessary to know if the flows are a resource consumed by a team or a product generated by a team. According to the economic or productive structure of the system, the incoming or outgoing flows in each of the pieces of equipment that make it up have been classified as resources, products, and wastes or losses. The product (P) of a piece of equipment represents the desired useful effect it provides, according to its purpose. The resource (R) represents what is consumed to produce the product. But equipment can also have outgoing flows into the environment that have the character of waste or loss (with or without material flow), that is, without any useful effect (useless outputs); their set is known as the residue (I) of the team. This way, all equipment can be represented synthetically according to Figure 2.

Figure 2. Global IWERS flows

R , P , I are expressed in terms of exergy flows, as the sum of incoming flows classified as resources, products, or wastes minus the sum of outgoing flows of the same class. That is to say:

$$\dot{R} = \sum \dot{B}_R^+ - \sum \dot{B}_R^- \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{P} = \sum \dot{B}_P^- - \sum \dot{B}_P^+ \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{I} = \sum \dot{B}_I \quad (6)$$

Exergetic or rational performance of the IWERS

The exergetic performance is defined as the ratio between the exergy of the products obtained and that of the resources consumed. It is calculated according to the following equation:

$$z = \frac{\dot{P}}{\dot{R}} \quad (7)$$

The unitary exergetic consumption of the IWERS and of each component is the inverse of the exergetic performance. Therefore, it is calculated as:

$$k = \frac{\dot{R}}{\dot{P}} \quad (8)$$

Exergetic cost

The exergy cost of an exergetic flow n is defined as the exergy required to obtain that flow. It is depicted as B_n^* . The exergetic cost is an internal cost of the system, which depends on the exergy to be produced and the specific technology used, and which varies from case to case. It is necessary to point out that in a system, the energy consumed to produce an input to the system is not only generally unknown, but also depends on the process followed and is something foreign to the system. It is therefore an exergetic external cost that should not be included in the analysis because it does not affect the system. Therefore, the inputs to the system are assigned exergetic costs equal to their exergy: $B_{inlet}^* = \dot{B}_{inlet}$. The condition of nullity of the exergetic cost of the waste must be extended to all its components. Therefore, $B_j^* = 0$. The following exergetic cost balance is also verified: $R^* = P^*$.

It is important to note that when a resource enters the system from the environment (crossing the system's control surface), its exergetic cost is equal to its exergetic flow. The exergy required to produce it is an external cost that does not affect the system being studied. Therefore, in this case, it is true that: $R^* = \dot{R}$. When carrying out the balance of exergetic cost, it is always true that the exergetic cost of incoming flows must be equal to that of the outgoing ones.

$$\sum B_P^{*+} = \sum B_P^{*-} \quad (9)$$

The exergetic cost vector denoted as $B_{(nx1)}^*$, is defined as follows:

$$A_{(m \times n)} \cdot B_{(nx1)}^* = 0_{(m \times n)} \quad (10)$$

The unit exergy cost of each flow

The unit exergy cost of a current n is defined as the exergy required to obtain one unit of exergy from it. This is calculated using the following equation:

$$\kappa_n^* = \frac{B_n^*}{\dot{B}_n} \quad (11)$$

The expressions are calculated according to the equations:

$$R^* = \sum B_R^{*+} - \sum B_R^{*-} \quad (12)$$

$$P^* = \sum B_P^{*-} - \sum B_P^{*+} \quad (13)$$

$$I^* = \sum B_I^* \quad (14)$$

This unit cost includes the effect of the thermodynamic perfection of the process and the economic criteria used to determine exergetic costs. The thermodynamic perfection of the process increases as the unit cost decreases. It is important to note that when a team produces multiple products (n), the unit exergetic costs assigned to each product output of that team are equal.

$$\kappa_n^* = \frac{B_{product\ 1}^*}{B_{product\ 1}} = \frac{B_{product\ 2}^*}{B_{product\ 2}} = \dots \dots \dots = \frac{B_{product\ n}^*}{B_{product\ n}} \quad (15)$$

This is because the exergetic cost is distributed in proportion to the exergies of the outputs, which represent their respective useful energy flows.

The calculations were based on actual operating and electrical consumption data collected over a one-year period for each component. The IWERS analyzed was situated in a supermarket in northern Spain with two ovens, which experiences a temperate climate with warm winters and cool summers.

Exergy associated with the i-th material stream

The specific exergy related to the i-th material stream was computed using the following equation.

$$e_i = e_i^{PH} + e_i^{CH} + e_i^{KN} + e_i^{PT} \quad (16)$$

Because they have little bearing, the terms related to kinetic (e_i^{KN}) and potential exergy (e_i^{PT}) are disregarded. Since the chemical makeup of the fluids involved in the various systems did not change, the chemical exergy (e_i^{CH}) was likewise disregarded. In this manner, the following equation was used to determine the exergy related to the *i*-th material stream.

$$\dot{E}x_i = \dot{E}x_i^{PH} = e_i \cdot \dot{m}_i = \dot{m}_{fluid} \cdot [(h_i - h_0) - T_0 \cdot (s_i - s_0)] \quad (17)$$

The calculation of the exergy related to heat transfer was performed utilizing the subsequent equation.

$$\dot{E}x_{Q,j} = \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_j}\right) \cdot \dot{Q}_j \quad (18)$$

The heat transfer rate at the boundary of the control volume, where the temperature is T_j , is denoted as \dot{Q}_j . The ambient temperature (T_0) and the ambient pressure (P_0) are the temperature and pressure of the system boundaries outside the device.

3. Results and Conclusions

For each month of the year, Figure 3 shows the curve of total annual exergy destruction in IWERS calculated using the methodology specified.

Figure 3. Annual exergy destruction in IWERS

Exergy destruction in IWERS was directly proportional to the ambient temperature. Therefore, this destruction was less during the coldest months of the year.

Figure 4 reflects the relative exergy destruction in the IWERS components.

Figures 4. Relative exergy destruction in the IWERS components

The equipment with the highest exergy destruction was the steam condenser, reaching close to 45% in each condenser during the coldest months of the year. The electric boilers were the second most inefficient equipment, with a destruction of 4% in each boiler during the warmer months. On the other hand, the water pump was the most efficient equipment, with values like those obtained in the DHW Tank. Furthermore, it was observed that, unlike electric boilers, the water pump, DHW tank, and steam condensers were more efficient during the summer months. The exergy destruction was mainly generated in the steam condensers, with values ranging between 84-85%. Therefore, action should be taken to improve these values in these areas.

Figure 5 shows the exergetic or rational performance of the IWERS for each month of the year. The performance ranges from 20.7% to 24.6%, with higher values observed during the colder months.

Figures 5. Exergetic performance of the IWERS (%)

Table 1 shows the annual unitary exergetic consumption of the IWERS and its components. Both for the system as a whole and for all its elements, the highest values were obtained in the warm months. The only exception was the DHW Tank, which obtained higher unitary exergetic consumption values during the colder months.

Table 1. Annual unitary exergetic consumption of the IWERS and its components

	Electric Boiler (3 units)	DHW Tank	Water Pump	Steam Condenser (2 units)	IWERS
January	2.649	0.352	1.073	8.557	4.072
February	2.679	0.351	1.074	8.590	4.095
March	2.818	0.346	1.076	8.746	4.203
April	2.883	0.344	1.077	8.815	4.254
May	3.119	0.336	1.081	9.055	4.427
June	3.412	0.327	1.086	9.332	4.636
July	3.656	0.320	1.090	9.545	4.799
August	3.707	0.319	1.090	9.585	4.833
September	3.518	0.324	1.088	9.425	4.708
October	3.187	0.334	1.082	9.122	4.477
November	2.850	0.345	1.077	8.779	4.227
December	2.693	0.350	1.074	8.607	4.107

Table 2 shows the monthly unit exergetic cost for each flow. The highest values were the inlet flow to the tank from the steam condenser, followed by the inlet and outlet flows of the water

pump. These values were higher in the cold months in the case of the inlet flow to the tank and lower in the case of the flows passing through the water pump. Additionally, it was noted that the exergetic cost per unit of product (flow 6) increases by up to 4.2% during the summer.

Table 2. Monthly unit exergetic cost for each flow

	B_1^*	B_2^*	B_3^*	B_4^*	B_{4A}^*	B_5^*	B_6^*	B_7^*	B_8^*	B_9^*
January	0	4.50	65.38	39.37	39.57	30.51	25.81	0	4.50	0.20
February	0	4.50	65.33	39.37	39.57	30.46	25.76	0	4.50	0.20
March	0	4.50	65.19	39.43	39.63	30.26	25.56	0	4.50	0.20
April	0	4.50	65.14	39.47	39.67	30.17	25.47	0	4.50	0.20
May	0	4.50	64.99	39.61	39.81	29.88	25.18	0	4.50	0.20
June	0	4.50	64.89	39.82	40.02	29.57	24.87	0	4.50	0.20
July	0	4.50	64.88	40.03	40.23	29.35	24.65	0	4.50	0.20
August	0	4.50	64.86	40.06	40.26	29.30	24.60	0	4.50	0.20
September	0	4.50	64.88	39.91	40.11	29.47	24.77	0	4.50	0.20
October	0	4.50	64.97	39.67	39.87	29.80	25.10	0	4.50	0.20
November	0	4.50	65.16	39.45	39.65	30.21	25.51	0	4.50	0.20
December	0	4.50	65.31	39.37	39.57	30.44	25.74	0	4.50	0.20

Including equipment upstream of the process increased the exergy cost of the output, reflecting the destruction of exergy in the incorporated equipment. This is known as the internalization of irreversibility and external exergetic costs, also referred to as the substitution theorem. Thermo-economic diagnostic procedures in the literature assume that specific resource consumption of components is crucial for interpreting the effects of dysfunction and tracing the sources of anomalies. However, the actual interactions between components can cause changes in specific consumption and obscure the root cause of dysfunction, which presents a primary challenge to effectively applying these approaches.

The thermodynamic analysis could be enhanced by studying the annual behavior of the IWERS in various climatic conditions and analyzing different food store locations. This would provide more data to improve the system's applicability and its components.

Data Availability

There is no data available.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declare that he has no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Sala, L., & Picallo, A. (2020). Operational diagnosis of thermal installations in buildings. *Exergy Analysis and Thermoconomics of Buildings*, 721-788. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-12-817611-5.00009-6
- [2] Baghernejad, A., & Aslanzadeh, E. (2022). Application of multiobjective optimization in thermal design and analysis of complex energy systems. *Multi-Objective Combinatorial Optimization Problems and Solution Methods*, 211-237. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-12-823799-1.00001-2
- [3] Tsatsaronis, G., & Czielsa, F. (2009). Energetic and exergetic analysis of complex systems. *Encyclopedia of life support systems (EOLSS)*. Exergy, energy systems analysis and optimization. Vol 1. Oxford, UK: Eolss Publishers, 121-223.
- [4] Picallo-Perez, A., Sala, J. M., Portillo, L. D., & Vidal, R. (2021). Delving into thermoconomics: a brief theoretical comparison of thermo-economic approaches for simple cooling systems. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 2, 656818. DOI: 10.3389/frsus.2021.656818
- [5] Erlach, B., Serra, L., & Valero, A. (1999). Structural theory as standard for thermoconomics. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 40(15-16), 1627-1649. DOI: 10.1016/S0196-8904(99)00057-6
- [6] Bejan, A., Tsatsaronis, G., Moran, M. (1996). *Thermal design and optimization*. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- [7] Kim, D. J. (2010). A new thermo-economic methodology for energy systems. *Energy*, 35(1), 410-422. DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2009.10.008
- [8] Special Issue "Thermoconomics for Energy Efficiency". (2016). *Entropy*.

- [9] Tsatsaronis, G. (1993). Thermoeconomic analysis and optimization of energy systems. *Progress in energy and combustion science*, 19(3), 227-257. DOI: 10.1016/0360-1285(93)90016-8
- [10] Hekmatshoar, M., Deymi-Dashtebayaz, M., Gholizadeh, M., Dadpour, D., & Delpisheh, M. (2022). Thermoeconomic analysis and optimization of a geothermal-driven multi-generation system producing power, freshwater, and hydrogen. *Energy*, 247, 123434. DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2022.123434
- [11] Liu, B., Lu, H., & Feng, L. (2022). Thermoeconomic analysis and Multi-Objective optimization for the synthesis of green hydrogen and three different products via a novel energy system. *Fuel*, 327, 125003. DOI: 10.1016/j.fuel.2022.125003
- [12] Tsatsaronis, G. (1993). Thermoeconomic analysis and optimization of energy systems. *Progress in energy and combustion science*, 19(3), 227-257. DOI: 10.1016/0360-1285(93)90016-8
- [13] Wang, D., Ali, M. A., Alizadeh, A. A., Singh, P. K., Almojil, S. F., Alali, A. F., ... & Almohana, A. I. (2023). Thermoeconomic appraisal of a novel power and hydrogen cogeneration plant with integration of biomass and geothermal energies. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 52(C), 385-400. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.02.066
- [14] Picallo-Perez, A., Sala-Lizarraga, J. M., Escudero-Revilla, C., Hidalgo-Betanzos, J. M., & Ruiz de Vergara, I. (2022). Thermoeconomic analysis in Advanced cogeneration Systems in buildings. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 9, 802971. DOI: 10.3389/fenrg.2021.802971
- [15] de Faria, P. R., Barone, M. A., dos Santos, R. G., & Santos, J. J. C. (2023). The environment as a thermoeconomic diagram device for the systematic and automatic waste and environmental cost internalization in thermal systems. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 171, 113011. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.113011
- [16] Prol-Godoy, I., Picallo-Perez, A., Sala-Lizarraga, J. M., & Rey-Martínez, J. (2023). Experimental test of a building thermal system for preventive maintenance based on thermoeconomic analysis. *Energy Storage and Saving*. DOI: 10.1016/j.enss.2023.08.002

- [17] Gao, X., Niu, Z., Huang, X., Yang, X., & Yan, J. (2023). Thermo-economic assessments on building heating by a thermal energy storage system with metal foam. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 49, 103307. DOI: 10.1016/j.csite.2023.103307
- [18] Gürbüz, E. Y., Keçebaş, A., & Sözen, A. (2022). Exergy and thermoeconomic analyses of the diffusion absorption refrigeration system with various nanoparticles and their different ratios as work fluid. *Energy*, 248, 123579. DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2022.123579
- [19] Ríos-Fernández, J. C. (2019). A novel Integrated Waste Energy Recovery System (IWERS) by thermal flows: A supermarket sector case. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 19, 97-104. DOI: 10.1016/j.spc.2019.03.010
- [20] Cengel, Y. A., Boles, M. A., & Kanoğlu, M. (2011). *Thermodynamics: an engineering approach*, 5, 445. McGraw-hill, New York.
- [21] El-Sayed, Y. M. (2003). *The Thermoeconomics of Energy Conversions*. Elsevier, Oxford.
- [22] Lozano, M. A., & Valero, A. (1993). Theory of the exergetic cost, *Energy*, 18, 939-960. DOI:
- [23] Valero, A., Serra, L., Uche, J. (2006). Fundamentals of exergy cost accounting and Thermoeconomics. *Journal of Energy Resources and Technology-Transactions of the ASME*, 128 (1), 1-8. DOI: 10.1115/1.2134732
- [24] Montes, J. M., García, J., Querol, E. (2009). *Termoeconomía y optimización energética*. Fundación Gómez Pardo en colaboración con el Consejo Superior de Colegios de Ingenieros de Minas, Madrid.